

Valorization of Protein Materials Through Mechanochemistry and Self-Assembly

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The concept of combining mixing of solids by milling (a type of mechanochemistry) with aqueous self-assembly provides interesting possibilities for energy efficient production of advanced nanomaterials. Many proteins are outstanding building blocks for self-assembly, a prominent example being the conversion of proteins into protein nanofibrils (PNFs) - a structure related to amyloid fibrils. PNFs have attractive mechanical properties and have a tendency to form ordered materials. They are accordingly of interest as materials for bioplastics and potentially also for more high-tech applications. In this concept article we highlight our effort on valorization of such proteins with

hydrophobic organic compounds such as organic dyes and drug molecules, by developing scalable methodology combining mechanochemistry and self-assembly. Compared to more established methodology, mechanochemical methodology is a valuable complement as it allows potential scalable production of hybrids between e.g. proteins and highly hydrophobic compounds - a class of hybrid material that is difficult to access by other means. This may allow for development of sustainable processes for fabrication of advanced protein-based materials derivable from renewable source materials.

1. Introduction

Self-assembly is in principle an outstanding method for preparation of materials. As stated by Grzybowski *et al.* in a review article from 2009: "Self-assembly is the ultimate dream of a lazy scientist: just mix the components, and the forces of nature will assemble them into a desired structure."^[1] Within the context of sustainability, this statement can perhaps be rephrased as "Self-assembly is the ultimate dream of an energy conscious scientist" as many biogenic molecules (often obtainable as by-products or side streams from industrial processes) are superb "self-assemblers" in the ultimate "green solvent" water.^[2] Herein we propose that the procedures milling and self-assembly can be fruitfully combined into a powerful methodology for formation of (functionalized) biopolymeric materials. Milling is a standard laboratory procedure (that belongs to the scientific field mechanochemistry), and almost all labs have a mortar and pestle as part of their toolkit. This is a highly useful tool for preparing mixtures of solids and reducing particle size. Procedures involving grinding/milling has been used since ancient times. In a text from the 3rd–4th cent. CE the alchemist Zosimus of Panopolis claimed "what makes every work perfect is cooking and grinding", meaning that the combination of an initial grinding step followed by heating is

an excellent way to prepare materials.^[3] Milling is moreover often employed in pharmaceuticals where drugs with low solubility are milled with a water soluble matrix (often a water soluble polymer or surfactant).^[4] Similar processing can be employed for preparing aqueous dispersions of pigments. In short, milling is an excellent process for mixing of a wide variety of materials in diverse disciplines. And here interesting possibilities arise for the combination of mechanochemical processing and aqueous self-assembly: mill a material insoluble in water with a molecule capable of self-assembly in water. When water is added to the resulting mixture the water-soluble molecule may help to disperse the hydrophobic component in water, and when exposed to appropriate stimuli self-assembly may still occur, while the hydrophobic effect ensures that the hydrophobic component remains associated with the self-assembling system. Proteins, with their intrinsic amphiphilic nature, are excellent examples of hosts for this process. In this concept article the focus is on a combination of mechanochemistry and aqueous self-assembly of proteins. In Section 2 is given an introduction to proteins and their assembly into amyloid-related materials. A short overview of the relation between mechanochemistry, supramolecular chemistry and self-assembly is then presented in Section 3. In Section 4 is given a description of methodology, based on a combination of mechanochemistry and protein self-assembly, by which proteins and PNFs can be functionalized with a wide variety of hydrophobic materials. In Section 5 we give examples of how the presence of hydrophobic materials influences the properties of protein materials. In Section 6 different methods for functionalization of proteins and formation of functionalized PNFs are discussed and compared. In Section 7 are given examples of non-protein systems combining mechanochemistry and aqueous self-assembly. This is followed by a conclusions and outlook in Section 8.

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2. Proteins and Protein Nanofibrils

Proteins are among the most complex organic molecules, often having a well-defined structure (i.e., the native state) which is, however, only one of many possible conformations. Proteins moreover have a rich supramolecular chemistry and ability to self-assemble into supramolecular polymeric structures – where the individual protein corresponds to a monomer that aggregates into the supramolecular polymer.^[5] Many proteins can be isolated in large quantities from both natural sources and industrial waste and side-streams, making proteins an excellent potential feedstock for tomorrow's materials.^[6] For most applications in materials science individual protein molecules must be assembled into solid materials such as films and coatings, and in certain cases be functionalized with external agents. It is hence of great value to be able to modify the structural and physical properties of proteins. From this perspective, a given protein can be viewed as a base structure, with a certain set of chemical and physical properties. The protein structure can be modified employing both covalent and supramolecular approaches.^[7] In addition, due to the polymeric nature of proteins their structure can be modified by inducing the protein to undergo conformational changes, that may moreover increase the propensity of the protein to aggregate. This is a complex topic where the details will depend on the specific structure of the protein; however, many proteins display a sort of two-state character with two alternative stable and highly ordered structures - the native (monomeric) state and a fibrillar (polymeric) state known as amyloid.^[8] In addition, less ordered structures of amorphous character may be formed.^[9] Many proteins are known to form amyloid fibrils *in vivo* and are often associated with diseases. However, a wide variety of examples of functional amyloid^[10] (where the amyloid structure has a functional role in organisms) have been found. In addition, many non-disease related proteins can form amyloid fibrils *in vitro*, and hence be employed as building blocks for functional materials^[11] - interestingly this includes proteins obtained from industrial by-products^[12] and plant proteins^[13]. We hereafter designate such amyloid fibrils as protein nanofibrils (PNFs)^[14]. For many proteins, PNF formation can be induced simply by heating the protein in water at a pH far from the isoelectric point (typical conditions are heating at 80–90 °C and a pH close to 2). PNFs typically have diameters of about 5–

10 nm, lengths in the micrometer range, and have excellent mechanical properties with a strength similar to that of steel^[15]. Their high aspect ratio means that PNFs may form ordered liquid crystalline phases, which may be exploited for formation of hierarchically organized materials. In addition, PNFs contains various binding sites enabling both covalent and non-covalent functionalization (see Section 4 and 6 for further discussion). Many studies have demonstrated that PNFs can be employed as components in various types of macroscopic materials such as bioplastic films^[12,16] and fibers^[17]. In addition, PNFs have been demonstrated to be outstanding materials for water purification.^[18] PNFs readily form gels and are also investigated as biomaterials.^[19] In addition, the structural properties of PNFs make them attractive as scaffolds and templates for electrically conductive and/or luminescent materials/molecules potentially enabling relatively high-tech applications related to areas such as biosensing, electronics, and photonics.^[11,20] Accordingly, conversion of proteins into PNFs and/or their functionalization represents ways of potentially valorizing protein materials.^[21] Keeping in mind the possibility of employing low-cost proteins as a renewable feedstock for materials, it is of interest to develop scalable methodology for protein valorization.

3. Mechanochemistry and Self-Assembly

Mechanochemistry has a great potential for green synthesis and materials preparation (it is a solvent free technique, has a low energy cost, and is inherently scalable).^[22] Mechanochemistry can be performed by employing a mortar and pestle; however, various automated techniques are available with ball milling being the most common (Figure 1a).^[22d] Different configurations are possible - in a vibratory mill, milling jars containing milling balls are shaken at a set frequency, whereas in a planetary ball mill the milling jars are rotated horizontally. These three techniques are the most commonly employed but a variety of different equipment is available as described in various reviews.^[23] Mechanochemistry has recently received much interest in a wide range of areas including the transformation and valorization of biomass^[24] and synthetic organic chemistry and polymer chemistry.^[22,25] Mechanochemistry has been employed to form of a wide range of supramolecular host-guest complexes.^[26] Milling provides interesting possibilities for

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Figure 1. Illustration of different of milling devices/ instruments (a) Adapted with permission of the American Chemical Society (2020) from ref.^[22d]; Host compounds with a hydrophobic binding site and hydrophobic guest molecules mixed by grinding are dissolved in water forming host-guest complexes, that may undergo further self-assembly (b); Hydrophilic/amphiphilic compounds and hydrophobic molecules mixed by grinding are dissolved in water resulting in clusters with hydrophobic molecules as the core, surrounded by the Hydrophilic/amphiphilic compound. Upon appropriate stimuli the hydrophilic/amphiphilic compound may undergo self-assembly and structural changes that may lead formation of binding sites or cavities for the hydrophobic molecules (c).

mixing of hydrophilic and hydrophobic components. While these can be hard to mix as solutions, they can readily be mixed in the solid state by milling. The resulting complex may then be dissolved in water, where the hydrophilic host enables dispersion of the hydrophobic component in water. This approach is outlined schematically in Figure 1b, and examples will be given in Section 7. In addition, by employing hydrophilic/amphiphilic materials with a known capacity for self-assembly, the self-assembly process may result in structural changes in the hydrophilic material, for example by forming binding sites where the hydrophobic component may bind, as outlined schematically in Figure 1c. An especially challenging (regarding solubility) class of hydrophobic compounds are luminescent dyes, as these often have a large fraction of aromatic rings enabling efficient pi stacking. As a result, it is not uncommon to find dyes that are challenging to dissolve even in organic solvents. In addition to dyes, many important drug molecules and food additives are hydrophobic.^[27] On the other hand, the natural environment for biopolymers such as proteins is water, making mixing in solution phase of proteins and hydrophobic molecules challenging (as the hydrophobic effect will prevent dissolution of the hydrophobic component in water).

4. Mechanochemistry and Self-Assembly for Functionalization of Proteins and PNFs

Hybrids between luminescent dyes and proteins are interesting for a wide variety of applications, and functionalized PNFs have potential applications in organic electronics and photonics.^[20,28]

Due to the different polarity of proteins and many luminescent dyes such materials are often difficult to prepare employing solvent-based methodology. However, by employing the approach outlined schematically in Figure 2a such materials can be readily prepared. When co-grinding the protein and the hydrophobic compound (typically employing 1–2 weight % relative to the protein), for example by mortar and pestle (typically for 10 min) or by automated milling equipment such as a mixer mill (typically at a frequency of 30 Hz for a duration of 10 min), the hydrophobic compound is dispersed in the protein matrix. Upon addition of water, the resulting hybrid material is dissolved /dispersed in water, where the hydrophobic material can be assumed to be located within micelle-like structures formed by the protein.^[29] The protein accordingly acts as a surfactant resulting in an aqueous dispersion of protein particles containing aggregates of the organic dye with a protein coating.^[30] This corresponds to the schematic process outlined in Figure 2a up to, but not including the step labeled as fibrillation. Milling of dyes with proteins is a well-known technique for dispersing e.g., pigments in water, and such protein dispersions may have interesting properties in their own right.

For example, by employing the hydrophobic Rhodamine-derivative 14, the resulting protein-dye hybrid nanoparticles could be employed for selective colorimetric detection of copper (II).^[29] Meanwhile, if a protein capable of self-assembly into PNFs is employed this method can be employed to form functionalized PNFs. The whole process is outlined schematically in the top part of Figure 2a, while in the bottom part a specific experimental example is given regarding functionalization of hen egg white lysozyme (HEWL) with the laser dye DCM (5). When heated in aqueous acid the proteins unfold and rearranges into structures capable of self-assembly into PNFs. During the self-assembly process, as the hydrophobic material is insoluble in water, it will stay associated with the proteins ending up in the hydrophobic grooves of the fibrillar structure.^[31] We have demonstrated the generality of the method by preparing PNFs functionalized with a wide variety of hydrophobic compounds, and investigated various applications, as summarized in Figure 2 and 3 and Table 1.^[28a,29,31–32] The employed molecules include well known classes of laser dyes and drug molecules.^[32–33] As a general rule, before PNF formation the dyes are present as aggregates displaying a low quantum yield due to aggregation induced quenching. Upon PNF formation dyes can be dispersed within the PNF matrix giving rise to a much higher quantum yield. As shown in Figure 2b PNFs contain various structures where linear and thin dyes may bind that promote dispersion of dyes. In Figure 2b is shown an example involving the luminescent dye 6T (1) mixed with bovine insulin.^[31] Emission spectra of the sample before PNF formation (labeled as 0 h) displays a low quantum yield and a spectrum typical of aggregated 6T. As PNFs are formed there is a concomitant increase in quantum yield and the emission spectrum is typical of monomeric 6T. As the PNF structure contains binding sites in the form of hydrophobic grooves oriented along the long fibril axis, dyes such as 6T tend to align with the long axis parallel with the long fiber axis. In

Figure 2. Schematic illustration (upper part) and an example (lower part) of the self-assembly of proteins functionalized with hydrophobic dyes into PNFs. The protein is ground with a hydrophobic molecule; either with a shaker mill indicated by method 1 (the photograph shows a grinding cup with ground protein and dye) or method 2 (by mortar and pestle). For both methods grinding, dissolution, and filtration yields a clear solution. Upon heating the protein self-assembles into PNFs. (a); The fluorescence intensity of 6T@insulin as a function of incubation time (with 6T@PNF forming over time) (b), and a comparison between LD (linear dichroism), absorbance and excitation spectra obtained for a 6T@PNF sample (c). Adapted with permission from ref. [31]. Copyright (2014) Royal Society of Chemistry; PNFs functionalized with multiple dyes by Method A, (mixing three types of PNFs each functionalized with one type of dye) and method B (employing one type of PNF functionalized with three different dyes) and the corresponding fluorescence spectra and photos of the solution under daylight and UV light (d). Adapted with permission from ref. [32] Copyright (2021) American Chemical Society.

Figure 3. Chemical structures of studied compounds for functionalization of proteins/ PNFs. α -sexithiophene (1 or 6T), α -octithiophene (2 or 8T), pyrene (3), fluorol 555 (4 or F555), 4-Dicyanomethylene-2-methyl-6-p-dimethylaminostyryl-4H-pyran (5 or DCM), Nile red (6), (S)(+)-camptothecin (7), BTA-1 (8), fluorescent brightener 378 (9 or F378), para-sexiphenyl (10), Perylene diimide derivative (11), fluorescent hydantoin (12), paraffin (13), rhodamine dye derivative (14), and Iridium complexes (15, 16 and 17).

Table 1. Summary of employed combinations of proteins and hydrophobic compounds (numbers refer to numbering given in Figure 3) and the investigated type of application.

Protein	Molecular weight (KDa)	Isoelectric point	Hydrophobic compounds	Applications	Ref.
INS ^[a]	5.8	5.4	(1)	Methodology investigation	[31]
			(5), (6), (8), (9), (10)	Amyloid probe	[32a]
			(16), (17)	Methodology investigation	[32b]
			(15), (17)	White LED	[28a]
HEWL ^[b]	14.6	10.7	(1), (2), (3), (6), (7)	Methodology investigation	[32c]
			(1), (13)	Air water interface films	[32d]
			(5)	Air water interface films for stimulated emission	[32d]
			(11)	Bioplastics	[32e]
			(14)	Detection of Cu ²⁺	[29]
			(4), (6), (9)	White LED coating	[32f]
BLG ^[c]	18.4	4.8	(1), (13)	Air water interfaces films	[32d]
			(5)	Air water interface films for stimulated emission	[32d]
			(12)	Drug delivery/ release	[32g]

In abbreviations: [a] INS = Bovine insulin; [b] HEWL = Hen egg white lysozyme; [c] BLG = beta-lactoglobulin.

Figure 2c is shown an example where the spectrum labeled as LD-signal is the absorption from a flow linear dichroism measurement, where the sample is rotated in a Couette cell leading to alignment of anisotropic objects such as PNFs. The strong signal stems from light absorption of 6T molecules with their long axis parallel with the long fibril axis (corresponding to binding in mode 1 as indicated in Figure 2a). If compared with the spectrum labeled absorption (corresponding to a normal UV-Vis absorption measurement), differences can be observed indicating that not all 6T-molecules have an anisotropic arrangement. On the other hand, the excitation spectrum is matching well with the LD-spectrum meaning the anisotropic 6T-population has a high quantum yield.

PNFs can moreover be employed as a template where different agents can be co-assembled resulting in multiply functionalized PNFs.^[34] Yuan and Solin employed mechanochemical methodology i.e. co-grinding of lysozyme proteins and dyes with a weight ratio of 100:1 with a mortar and pestle followed by self-assembly to prepare multiply functionalized PNFs where the three dyes functioned as a Förster Resonance Energy Transfer (FRET) system allowing for conversion of UV-light to white light (Figure 2d).^[32f] By slight modifications in the preparative procedure, it is possible to influence the extent of FRET. When comparing a mixture of three PNFs, where each PNF is functionalized with one type of dye (indicated as method A), and PNFs containing a statistical mixture of the three dyes (indicated as method B) the sample prepared by method B displays a higher degree of FRET (Figure 2d). These types of materials can then be incorporated into gels that can be used as light-conversion coatings on commercial UV LEDs in order to enable emission of white light (see Figure 5c).

If biologically active compounds are employed, the functionalized PNF materials can potentially be employed for drug delivery. By mixing beta-lactoglobulin (BLG) with the luminescent hydantoin-derivative 12, materials were prepared where

the functionalized proteins were incorporated into a hydrogel.^[32g] The release properties of the hydantoin-derivative could be influenced by the state of the protein. Employing hydrogels with functionalized BLG gave a relatively fast release (equilibrium reached after 30 h with an 84% release), whereas conversion of the protein to PNFs lead to slower release (equilibrium reached after 50 h with a release of 84% at pH 7 and 78% at pH 2) of the hydantoin-derivative from the hydrogel.

5. Modifying PNF Properties with Hydrophobic Materials

It should be noted that the presence of the hydrophobic material may perturb the self-assembly process, giving opportunities for preparation of new types of materials already when forming PNFs. Bäcklund and Solin have demonstrated that hydrophobic molecules may influence the structure and properties of products formed by self-assembly of bovine insulin, as shown in Figure 4.^[35] While forming PNFs from bovine insulin there is a strong tendency to form a related spherulite structure with an amorphous core region surrounded by radially oriented amyloid.^[36] When this process is occurring for bovine insulin spherulites with a diameter of up to 150 μm is formed (Figure 4, left side). Under the same conditions, but employing protein mixed with an oligothiophene (6T) spherulites with diameters up to 1 mm are formed (Figure 4, right side).^[35] The formation of spherulites can be viewed as a side-reaction that can often be suppressed if the protein dispersion is stirred during the PNF-formation process.

The self-assembly of protein into PNFs in aqueous solution, results in a colloidal dispersion of PNFs. When employing PNFs functionalized with hydrophobic dyes, the presence of dyes

Figure 4. The effect of 6T on the self-assembly of insulin in 25 mM HCl with schematic drawing and polarized light microscopy and fluorescent light microscopy images. Polarized light microscopy images of reaction solutions with and without 6T, after 12 hours of heat treatment at 65 °C. At the bottom is shown the corresponding images when the samples are irradiated with 420 nm light. Adapted with permission from ref.^[33] Copyright (2015) Royal Society of Chemistry.

may influence the colloidal properties of such PNF dispersions. We have published a clear demonstration of this effect, with a key result shown in Figure 5a.^[32d] PNFs incorporating hydrophobic compounds show an increased tendency to aggregate at the air-water interface, resulting in the formation of thin films (i.e. dense hydrogels) at the interface. Unmodified PNFs (without the hydrophobic dye) have a much weaker propensity to form such air-water interface films. The shape of the container can influence the PNF packing. In a square container optically anisotropic domains (with aligned PNFs) spanning square millimeter areas (although with defects) are formed, as demonstrated by polarized light microscopy images (obtained at a relative orientation of 0° and 45°) on films obtained from 6T@PNFs. When employing anisotropic dye molecules, as individual dye molecules tend to be oriented along the long PNF axis, whole ensembles of dyes become aligned and, as a result, display emission of polarized light. Such air-water interface films also form from PNFs functionalized with the laser dye

Figure 5. Examples of films/gels prepared from functionalized PNFs. A photograph of dispersion of functionalized PNFs (1@PNF) and the corresponding film formed at air-water interface and a photo of an isolated film. Polarized light microscopy (POM) image of films (formed from 1@PNF) formed in a square container; as well as polarized fluorescence spectra of a 1@PNF film (a). Adapted with permission from ref.^[32d]. Copyright (2021) American Chemical Society; Schematic drawing of the preparation of bioplastic by drop-casting, and a photo of a mechanically flexible bioplastic film prepared from functionalized PNFs (by compound 11) and POM images of a film prepared from PNFs (without dye) and PVA-GLY, or 11@PNFs and PVA-GLY, and the actuation properties of the corresponding films (b). Adapted with permission from ref. [32e]. Copyright (2022) Wiley-VCH GmbH; Photos of a dye functionalized PNF-based LED coating, and LEDs with and without a coating. The corresponding fluorescence spectra under LED-illumination is shown below. The inset shows the emission spectrum of the UV-LED in the absence and presence of the coating (c). Adapted with permission from ref.^[32f] Copyright (2021) American Chemical Society.

DCM. These films displayed stimulated emission, and hence have potential as solid-state organic dye laser materials.^[32d]

There has been much recent interest in employing PNFs as components of bioplastics.^[12,16] The PNF-PVA system can be employed to form plastic films by casting,^[32e] where the presence of hydrophobic substances in PNFs has dramatic effects on the properties of the films. PVA is a water soluble polymer^[37] and PVA-based plastics often suffers from poor stability towards water. Addition of PNFs functionalized with a PDI-dye (structure 11 in Figure 3) results in films that are stable in water (for at least 1 month whereas controls with PNFs (without the hydrophobic dye) disintegrate within minutes). PNF-PVA films tend to become brittle when dried; however, this problem can be solved by addition of glycerol (GLY) as a softener. An example of a free-standing film is shown in Figure 5b. The film is mechanically flexible and can be folded into different shapes that can be glued together by applying water. If put into water, such films will swell but remain structurally intact. As a result, a film of suitable geometry can be folded into e.g. a box-shape where the edges can be glued together by applying water. Upon evaporation of water the films adhere together. Interestingly, addition of PDI-dye 11 promotes structural organization of PNFs in the films. In Figure 5b is shown polarized light microscopy images at 0° and/or 45° orientation for films made from 11@PNFs. For comparison is shown a film made from PNFs with no hydrophobic dye. In the presence of the hydrophobic dye an anisotropic phase is clearly formed, whereas there is no indication of structural order in the case of PNFs without hydrophobic dye. The structural organization in these films will influence macroscopic properties. For example, if deposited onto an aluminum film, evaporation of water will preferably occur from the film surface exposed to air. This will lead to a shrinking of the film that in turn leads to actuation effect.

As can be seen in Figure 5b the actuation effect is more pronounced for the film incorporating the dye. Moreover, due to the anisotropy films incorporating the PDI-dye display emission of polarized light. In addition to films, the PNF-PVA-glycerol system can be molded into other shapes. For example, the multiply functionalized PNFs described in Figure 2d, when mixed with PVA and glycerol, can be converted into gels that can be molded into LED coatings that can be put on top of a UV-LED thereby enabling conversion of UV-light to white light (Figure 5c).^[32f]

6. Comparison of Methodology for Functionalization of Proteins and PNFs

Proteins and PNFs contain a wide variety of functional groups (e.g. R-SH; R-OH, R-COOH, R-NH₂) that can be used as handles for attachment of molecules by covalent bonds. In addition, PNFs contain fine structures in the form of hydrophobic grooves, formed as a result of the presence of extended β -sheet structures, which are suitable binding sites for hydrophobic molecules such as organic dyes. As described by Woolfson and

Mahmoud,^[38] functionalization of PNFs can be divided into the two main families post-assembly and co-assembly (Table 2).

In the case of post-assembly methods, the preformed PNFs are treated with the functionalization agent. The functional moieties can be attached to preformed PNFs by covalent chemistry. A wide variety of approaches are possible, including so-called click chemistry by which a wide variety of functionalities have been coupled to amyloid fibrils containing alkyne functional groups.^[39] The post-assembly approach can also involve non-covalent binding. This approach is strongly related to the standard methodology employed for detection of amyloid in the context of diseases - here a water-soluble dye is mixed with an aqueous dispersion of PNFs, and an equilibrium is established between free and bound dye.^[40] Classical dyes for amyloid detection are Thioflavin T (ThT) and Congo red.^[41] Recently, a large variety of novel probes have been investigated, for example based on conjugated polythiophenes.^[42] From a material science perspective, the PNFs can be viewed to function as a template for dispersion and organization of luminescent dye molecules. For dyes with only slight solubility in water a co-solvent miscible with water can be employed, for example DMSO or ethanol.^[32a,43] The co-assembly approach typically involves the covalent functionalization of the proteins followed by PNF formation. The covalent modification can be performed by organic chemistry or synthetic biology approaches.^[44]

A comparison of the different methodologies, with a summary of the discussion are provided in Table 2. It should be noted that this comparison is complicated by the dual nature of protein research. On the one hand, proteins are often functionalized in order to enable mechanistic studies of biochemical processes. These processes are carried out in small scale, often employing relatively expensive dyes with installed spacers enabling efficient coupling to proteins. On the other hand, other proteins are investigated as bulk materials, for example as packaging materials. In this case covalent modification is often employed in order to influence physical properties such as the barrier properties of protein-based films.^[45] In this situation, low-cost reagents are employed in e.g. alkylation and acylation reactions. Accordingly, if suitable functionalization agents are available (for example an organic moiety with a proper functional group enabling efficient coupling to the protein), co-assembly process is in principle an excellent method for functionalization. However, a complication is that the added functionalized moieties may disturb PNF formation. In addition, these methods require the installment of a suitable spacer before the functional moiety can be conjugated to the protein. While many dyes with proper spacers are commercially available, these tend to be costly and therefore not suitable for functionalization in large scale. In addition, they are often intended for studies of biomolecular mechanism or imaging and may not have the suitable photophysical properties for applications related to for example photonics.

A further issue is that while covalent functionalization of proteins will occur at suitable functional groups within the protein, PNF functionalization may be complicated by the tendency for high molecular weight proteins to undergo

Table 2. Summary of the PNF functionalization methods.

Functionalization methods	Interaction type	Schematic illustration of functionalization of PNFs	Scale	Structural control	Flexibility
Co-assembly	Protein and FA conjugated by covalent bond		Small to medium	High (but can be complicated by non-selective attachment or protein hydrolysis during PNF formation)	Low, requires reagents that can be linked to the protein by covalent bond
Post-assembly (covalent bond)	PNF and FA conjugated by covalent bond		Small to medium	High (but can be complicated by non-selective attachment)	Low, requires reagents that can be linked to the protein by covalent bond
Post-assembly (physical interaction)	Non-covalent interaction		Small to large	Medium (FA will bind to PNF in an equilibrium process)	High, requires water soluble reagents that will bind to PNF
Mechanochemistry and self-assembly	Non-covalent interaction		Medium to large	Low (FA often present as aggregates before PNF formation; Mixture of structures after PNF formation)	High, requires hydrophobic reagents. May also be beneficial for reagents slightly soluble in water

[a] FA, abbreviation of functionalized agents.

hydrolysis simultaneously with PNF formation. The functionalization agent may accordingly end up on a peptide fragment not incorporated into PNFs. Water soluble functionalization reagents can of course be trivially mixed with proteins simply by processing in water. The water-soluble reagent may then bind to PNFs through non-covalent interactions. On the other hand, a hydrophobic dye and a protein are difficult to mix in water, but they are trivial to mix by milling in the solid state. The protein, to be converted to PNFs then fulfills a dual role.

It acts as a surfactant enabling the dispersion of the dye in water. However, the protein is still capable of self-assembly into PNFs, resulting in PNFs functionalized with the hydrophobic dye. In an aqueous environment the hydrophobic effect will promote the association of the dye and the protein meaning that a wide range of both hydrophobic compounds and proteins can be used. As the hydrophobic effect is strongly related to entropy of water the structural detail of the hydrophobic compound is relatively unimportant. The methodology is accordingly extremely flexible regarding the types of hydrophobic materials that can be employed. Although operationally simple, complex materials can rapidly be prepared and evaluated. As described in Section 3, a wide variety of hydrophobic compounds can be employed, endowing PNFs with novel functionality. The mechanochemical mixing approach allows highly hydrophobic molecules, that may be hard to dissolve even in organic solvents, to be processed into aqueous dispersions. Even if approaches based on co-solvents can be used in certain cases, this means that materials scientists wishing to employ PNF materials often cannot work with the starting materials they would like to, but only with those that have high enough solubility in water. However, a potential drawback is a relatively low degree of structural control regarding dye binding. Our results indicate that linear and flat dyes will tend to bind with their long axis parallel to the long fibril axis (in a similar manner as e.g. the water-soluble amyloid staining reagents Congo Red and ThT).^[31] However, further studies are required on the nature of hydrophobic molecules binding to PNFs. Another limitation of both the co-assembly and mechanochemical methodology is that the hydrophobic molecule will be present during PNF formation that will typically be performed at a low pH. This means acid sensitive molecules may decompose during PNF formation. Another issue is the possibility of degradation/structural change of the proteins during milling.^[46] As the proteins will desaturate and often hydrolyze during PNF formation this issue may not be serious. However, a protein structural change may lead to materials of low solubility in water which may complicate processing.

Moreover, as described in Section 4, the presence of hydrophobic compounds provides opportunities to influence the assembly of PNFs into macroscopic materials. With the aim of developing a circular economy, one interesting option is to employ proteins from sustainable resources as raw materials.^[6a] The required characteristics of a material will vary depending on its intended use and various methods have been developed in order to influence/optimize the properties of protein-based materials. It will then be valuable to have a large toolbox

enabling addition of functionality and tuning of materials properties. The low-cost and sustainable protein sources and easy processible mechanochemical methodology offers a path to scalable production and even industrialization.

7. Other Systems

While the focus of this article has been on mechanochemistry and proteins and their self-assembly into PNFs the described methodology can be employed also for other systems. This type of methodology has been investigated for formation of host-guest complexes between cyclodextrins^[47] or cucurbiturils^[48] and various hydrophobic compounds including fullerenes. The resulting host: guest complex can be dissolved in water, where the hydrophilic host enables dispersion of the hydrophobic component in water. This approach is outlined schematically in Figure 1b. However, the host: guest complex may also act as a starting point for self-assembly into more complex materials. This phenomenon has for example been observed with cyclodextrins, where aggregate formation is greatly enhanced on host: guest complex formation, and the extent of aggregation increases with increasing host concentration. In addition to hosts with well-defined binding sites (such as cyclodextrins) one can envision the use of other types of hydrophilic/amphiphilic materials. Such materials could then be milled with hydrophobic components and upon addition of water help to disperse the hydrophobic component in water, as outlined schematically in Figure 1c. A specific example is provided in Figure 6. As an alternative to normal surfactant molecules, aromatic amphiphiles with a bent geometry has been employed for encapsulating various hydrophobic compounds. A method based on grinding has been developed where the aromatic amphiphile and the guest are co-ground in the solid state, and upon solvation in water host-guest complexes are formed where multiple amphiphilic molecules assemble into a cage-like structure, thereby encapsulating the hydrophobic molecule allowing their dispersion in water. The resulting supramolecular structures often display unique physical properties not observed in bulk solution or the solid state. For example, by forming host-guest complexes where the aromatic amphiphiles encapsulated antiaromatic norcorrole Ni(II) complexes the authors could investigate formation of norcorrole dimers within the cage and the effect on photophysical properties (Figure 6a).^[49] In another study the authors were able to form aqueous dispersions of europium complexes that displayed a high quantum yield in water (Figure 6b)^[50]. The authors could also form aqueous dispersions of perylene bisimides and nanographenes employing methodology based on grinding.^[51]

8. Concluding Remarks and Outlook

Self-assembly is in principle a powerful method for preparation of materials but requires proper building blocks. As many biogenic materials display an outstanding capacity for self-

Figure 6. Formation of a micellar capsule $(18)_n$ from polyaromatic amphiphile 18 and preparation of host-guest complexes $(19)_m@(18)_n$ in water (a). Reproduced with permission from ref.^[49]. Copyright (2022) American Chemical Society. Encapsulation of Eu(III)-complexes 20 by amphiphile 21, with emission spectra ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 375 \text{ nm}$) for the complex 21:20a in water and only 20a dissolved in a mixture of water and acetonitrile (b). Reproduced with permission from ref.^[50]. Copyright (2018) Royal Society of Chemistry.

assembly, this gives interesting possibilities for developing new (nano)materials by energy efficient processes. A prominent example is the conversion of proteins into protein nanofibrils (PNFs). Many different proteins have been demonstrated to form such fibrils including common proteins available in large quantities such as bovine insulin, beta-lactoglobulin, hen egg white lysozyme as well as industrial by-products or side streams such as whey protein isolate and soy protein isolate. This is an active research area with new results appearing regularly. Herein we have described the concept of combining an initial mixing step by milling of proteins and hydrophobic compounds, with a follow-up step involving aqueous self-assembly of proteins into PNFs. As a wide variety of dyes, nutrients or drugs are hydrophobic this methodology complements other options such as attachment of the functionalization agent to the protein with a covalent bond, or the use of water-soluble reagents that will bind to the protein. The methodology has high generality, and a wide variety of hydrophobic molecules has

been combined with three different proteins. Interestingly the presence of the hydrophobic materials may influence the colloidal properties of the PNF dispersion, providing an additional method in addition to standard approaches such as varying of ionic strength and pH. Mixing of solids by milling is a highly general process that moreover has a high tolerance of impurities. As eventual future industrial applications will benefit from the use of protein isolates or protein concentrates this is an important aspect. We have in Section 7 also made a short description of grinding of hydrophobic compounds with non-protein self-assembly systems that are very different from the protein-based systems described in Sections 4 and 5. It is hence likely that the methodology can be expanded to include a wide variety of self-assembly systems, some suitable for green chemistry and relevant for sustainability; others enabling fundamental studies of molecules/materials of low solubility. While the methodology is operationally simple, the underlying processes are highly complex and further studies about mechanistic details are needed.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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